

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SOLITARY LUNG NODULE CLASSIFICATION USING DIFFERENT FUNCTIONS OF BACK PROPAGATION NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

One of the deadliest diseases across the global human population is lung cancer. Computed Tomography (CT) is preferred over X-ray detection for lung cancer to obtain improved accuracy. In this paper, a comparison is made among different training functions of Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) for classifying the solitary lung nodule as normal and abnormal. Gaussian filter is used for image pre-processing. The lung parenchyma region is identified using Active Contour Model (ACM). The feature extraction process uses Gray-level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) method. The BPNN classifier confirms whether the nodule is normal or abnormal.

Key words: Computed Tomography, Active Contour Model, Classification, Back Propagation Neural Network.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of lung cancer is a serious health concern among human being. The death rate due to lung cancer is very high when compared to other types of cancer [1]. The next 5-year survival rate of this type of cancer reduces if it is diagnosed at a very late stage [2]. The size of the lung nodule will be an indicator to determine the survival rate. If the lung nodule detection is done at a premature stage, the chance of complete cure is very high.

A lung nodule can be defined as having pivotal opacity of 3 to 30 mm diameter nodules. If the sizes are less than 3 mm, then they are named as micro-nodules. If the sizes are greater than 30 mm, then they are named as “mass” [3]. Based on the location, the lung nodules can be classified [4]. These lung nodules may not touch with nearby structures with well bounded nodules. Juxta-pleural nodules are attached to lung wall and Juxta-vascular nodules are

attached to blood vessels. These nodules can be classified as solid, sub-solid and non-solid based on the intensity profile [5].

To determine the malignancy factor of the disease, calculating the size of the nodule with utmost care is important. If the nodules are measured manually, inaccuracy may occur [6, 7]. Besides this, if the nodules are detected by manual methods then problems such as human perception difference and errors in handling the image lead to inefficient diagnosis [8]. Hence it is imperative to have automated strategies to locate the pulmonary nodules to improve the accuracy.

Computed Tomography (CT) is one of the imaging modalities which detect affected nodules at earlier stages [9]. A major challenge is to detect, segment, and classify the nodules whether it is normal or abnormal. This eases the diagnosis effort of the radiologists in locating the precise abnormality. Systems which perform based on these techniques are called as Computer Aided Detection (CAD) systems used to reduce the work load of radiologists and help to identify the nodules accurately [10].

In this paper, a Gaussian filter is used for pre-processing the input image. The active contour model (ACM) has been used for segmentation. The second order textural features which are obtained from Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). Back propagation Neural Network has been used to classify the nodules into normal and abnormal. For training the back propagation neural network, different training functions are used and their performance has been analyzed in the application of lung nodule classification.

2. RELATED WORKS

Samuel G. Armato et al. proposed an automated detection of pulmonary nodules on CT scans. The diameter of the nodules considered for this research work was 3.1 to 27.8 mm. For separating the thorax region from background, they constructed diagonal gray-level profile. In order to segment the lungs, a grey-level histogram was constructed. For detecting nodule candidates from the segmented lungs multiple grey-level threshold method was adopted. Features such as volume, sphericity, maximum compactness and mean grey level features were extracted from the nodule candidates. Linear discriminant classifier was deployed to differentiate normal nodules from the abnormal ones in [11]. In this article an overall sensitivity of 70% for nodule detection along with an average of 3 false-positive findings per section are obtained.

Kenji Suzuki et al. introduced massive training based ANN to detect lung nodules in CT imaging. In this paper, the author introduced a technique called multiple massive training artificial neural networks (MTANN). The classifier consists of many MTANNs connected concurrently. The overall sensitivity is 80.3% [12].

Elizabeth et al developed a computer aided diagnosis system for the diagnosis of lung cancer in CT images. Lung boundary extraction considered as pre-processing. For this, the threshold and greedy snake algorithm are used. Nodule extraction uses the erosion filter and pruning process. Binary classification of nodules was performed by radial basis function neural network [13].

Ashis Kumar Dhara et al. reported a new classification methodology of lung CT images. This classification method uses LIDC data set for validation with 891 nodules. From the segmented nodules, 3D and 2D features such as the shape, texture, and margin are calculated. Features were selected based on 2-tailed student's t-test. SVM classifier was used to differentiate malignant nodules from benign nodules [14].

Tao Zhou et al. reported new features to find the pulmonary lesions. The 3D shape features such as External Spherical Volume, Surface-Centre Distance Standard Deviation and

External Rectangle Cross Line Distance were proposed. 3D intensity features such as Laplace Divergence Mean and Laplace Divergence Distance were proposed. Rough set feature-level fusion was used to retain feature properties without pre-knowledge. The kernel function of the SVM classifier was optimized with grid optimization model for classifying the candidate nodules as nodule and non-nodule [15].

3. METHODOLOGY

The detection of abnormal lung nodule consists of these following steps: acquisition and pre-processing of original image, lung region segmentation, feature extraction and classification. The technique is initiated with the pre-processing of image using Gaussian filter to remove the noise. The next process is ACM segmentation and Nodule detection followed by GLCM based feature extraction which is then fed into the classifier unit. The neural network employed is of BPNN type for the classification of lung nodule.

3.1. Image Acquisition and Pre-Processing

The lung CT images for analysis are obtained from cancer imaging archive (LIDC-IDRI). The format of the images from the database are of DICOM and have a size of 512 X 512 pixels which are converted to JPEG format for better results out of ACM segmentation process. The nodule sizes have a range of 3 to 30mm. The sample input is shown in figure 1.

Figure.1 Input image

The pre-processing is done using a Gaussian linear filter for better system performance and to improve contouring. Gaussian filter offers a blurring image of the edges, and reduces contrast. It is a low frequency filter which eliminates the high frequency noise components. The pre-processed pattern is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Filtered image

3.2. Segmentation

In this phase, the region of interest is extracted from the thorax region to obtain a relevant and simple image pattern. The resulting pixels in the specified area are all the same everywhere with respect the texture, colour, and grey level. Adjacent area will have differences in all the above features. Snakes algorithm, also called as active contour model (ACM) as in figure 3 is a structure in computer vision for contouring object boundaries from an attainable noisy image of two dimensions.

Figure 3 Active Contour Model (ACM) output

Area closing and opening are two significant operators from morphological point of view. These operations will drastically alter the bright pixels of the foreground image edges. Figure 4 illustrates the result of area closing process.

Figure 4 Area closing of lung image

3.3. Nodule Detection

Figure 5 Detected nodule

After the morphological process of area closing is completed, the next step is to detect the possible nodules. Here the gray scale image is obtained to find out the pixel count. The nodules whose size is in the range of 3 mm to 30 mm are considered. Then the image is converted to binary pattern from which the possible nodules are detected.

3.4. Feature extraction

After the detection of nodule, the image is used for feature extraction. There are specific algorithms in the area of image processing that are implemented to isolate or detect specified shapes or portions of digitized picture. The texture examination is carried out using GLCM approach. The features such as autocorrelation, contrast, dissimilarity, correlation, and etc., are calculated.

3.5. Classification

After extracting the features, the values are fed to the classifier. The classifier is the feed forward back propagation neural network. With different training functions of back propagation, the results are compared and tabulated. Neural networks are considered as modelling tools of nonlinear statistical data where the complicated relationships between outputs and inputs are modelled or patterns are determined. Back-propagation is one of the Artificial Neural Network which uses gradient as the function in the weight update process. It is a multilayer input/output network and also a supervised neural network. The aim of a supervised learning algorithm is to find a function that matches the given inputs to their correct targets. The sample architecture of feed forward Back Propagation Neural Network is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6 Sample architecture of feed-forward BPNN

3.6. Types of Training Function

1) TRAINBFG:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to BFGS quasi-Newton termed into TRAINBFG, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

2) TRAINBR:

Updating and biasing values corresponding to Levenberg-Marquardt optimization is known as TRAINBR, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

3) TRAINGDM:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to gradient descent with momentum is known as TRAINGDM, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

4) TRAINGDA:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to gradient descent method with adaptive learning rate is known as TRAINGDA, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

5) TRAINGDX:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to gradient descent momentum and an adaptive learning rate is known as TRAINGDX, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

6) TRAINRP:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to the resilient back propagation algorithm (R_{prop}) is known as TRAINRP, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

7) TRAINSCG:

Updating of weights and biasing values corresponding to the scaled conjugate gradient method is known as TRAINSCG, one of the network training functions available in BPNN.

Following are the training limits to consider.

- Maximum number of epochs
- Run time
- Minimum value achieved
- Minimal gradient value

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experiments were done on windows 7 operating system with i5 processor. The software used for doing the project is MATLAB. LIDC database is used. From the database, 500 images with solitary pulmonary nodules are taken. 70% of data has been used for training, 15% data has been used for testing and 15% data has been used for validation. The input image is pre-processed using Gaussian filter. ACM is used for separating the lung parenchyma region. The iteration value chosen is 200; the sigma value used here is 1.5. The mean value of the GLCM features for both normal nodule and abnormal nodule are listed in table 1.

Table 1 Feature extraction values

GLCM Features	Normal Nodule (Mean)	Abnormal Nodule (Mean)
Autocorrelation	0.723	0.045
Contrast	0.189	0.245
Dissimilarity	0.467	0.079
Correlation	0.580	0.944
Energy	0.389	0.945
Entropy	0.547	0.092
Homogeneity	0.548	0.982
Maximum Probability	0.485	0.943
Variance	0.743	0.042
Sum Average	0.824	0.043
Sum Variance	0.63	0.042
Sum Entropy	0.567	0.156

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The architecture used in BPNN is 12-12-2. Since 12 features are used, the input needs 12 neurons in each layer and output layer needs two neurons. It is a two level classification. The two classes are normal class and abnormal class. In this BPNN architecture different training algorithms are used. Seven different training functions are used. The performances of all training functions are shown in figure 7 and figure 8 respectively.

Figure 7 MSE versus epoch

Figure 8 MSE versus epoch

Table 2 lists the performance of different training functions in terms of mean squared error (MSE), gradient value, and number of iterations. The final result is the percentage of classification accuracy for all the training functions, among which the TRAINSCG function exhibits the best accuracy value.

Table 2 Performance of training functions

S. No.	Training Functions	MSE	Gradient	Iterations	Classification Accuracy
1	TRAINBFG	1.18 e-13	5.48 e-06	16	63%
2	TRAINBR	0.0356	1.28 e-18	7	68%
3	TRAINGDM	1.62 e-13	7.34 e-06	303	72%
4	TRAINGDA	1.01 e-13	8.30 e-06	52	70%
5	TRAINGDY	4.23 e-13	8.81 e-06	91	82%
6	TRAINRP	1.14 e-13	5.01 e-16	40	80%
7	TRAINSOG	3.12 e-25	6.87 e-12	7	85%

Figure 9 highlights the classification accuracy of various training functions and TRAINSOG offers a maximum of 85% which is the best among all the other functions.

Figure 9 Training function versus accuracy

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we compared different training functions of back propagation neural network for lung cancer detection at its initial state from the size of lung nodules. The approach uses the normal image processing procedure upon the lung regions of the CT image. The back propagation neural network used different training functions and the results are analysed and plotted. It is observed that a minimum number of iterations are obtained in TRAINBR and TRAINRP functions. The function TRAINGDM consumed maximum number of iterations which is a limitation. Minimum number of mean square error is observed in TRAINSOG. It is observed that TRAINSOG gives better performance with acceptable number of iterations, low mean square error and high classification accuracy.

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